

D6.2

OJS plugin for the EOSC Interoperability Framework on Research Product Publishing

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Abstract	This work describes several components aiming at the alignment with the EOSC Interoperability Framework on Research Product Publishing that was developed by Research Product Publishing Framework Working Group of EOSC Future Working Groups. The process of the selection of the most appropriate strategy for OJS implementation is described as well as particular components for OJS as the solution consists of multiple components.

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
DC	Dublin Core
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-IF	European Open Science Cloud-Interoperability Framework
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
JMEF	Journal Metadata Exchange Format
LDN	Linked Data Notification
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OJS	Open Journal Systems
PID	Persistent Identifier
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
WG	Working Group

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This work describes several components aiming at the alignment with the **European Open Science Cloud Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF) on Research Product Publishing**, developed by the **Research Product Publishing Framework Working Group** of the **EOSC Future Working Groups**. It provides an overview of the process that led to the selection of the most appropriate strategy for implementing the Open Journal Systems (OJS) components and describes the individual modules that together form a comprehensive interoperability solution.

At the beginning of the project, the **EOSC-IF on Research Product Publishing** had not yet been fully defined. The framework was finalized only after the project had already started. Consequently, it became evident that the planned activity would not focus on developing a single OJS plugin, but rather on establishing a **complex structure composed of multiple independent protocols**. Some of these protocols already had existing OJS plugins, while others were identified as areas requiring new developments.

The outcomes of the **Research Product Publishing Framework Working Group** included several recommendations¹ addressing metadata management, data handling, and interoperability across systems. The summary of outputs and recommendations consists of the following key areas:

1. Landscape study and scenarios
2. Recommended protocols for research product deposition in *push mode*
3. Recommended protocols for research product deposition in *pull mode*
4. Recommended protocols for accessing the content behind a Persistent Identifier (PID)
5. Recommended metadata exchange formats

We systematically analysed and implemented these aspects within the context of OJS. The structure of this deliverable follows the same logic as the Working Group's outputs, ensuring consistency and traceability. Each section refers to additional materials in which specific structures, protocols, and implementation details are described in greater depth.

¹ [EOSC RPPF WG - Landscape study](#)

2 INTEROPERABILITY GUIDELINES

The **European Open Science Cloud Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF) on Research Product Publishing** by the **Research Product Publishing Framework Working Group²** of **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Future Working Groups³**:

“The goal of the this working group (WG) is to define a Research Publishing framework to simplify the adoption of that practice, by enabling the services of research infrastructures to seamlessly integrate repository deposition workflows in the context of the EOSC.

Such an interoperability framework will consist in API and formats that will allow for the implementation of end-to-end research workflows with an on-demand (semi) automatic step of publishing that ensures the FAIRness of research outputs obtained thanks to the RI. After the first six months of activity, the WG plans to open the protocol specification for public consultation and suggest its inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

The WG will contribute to the areas of EOSC Exchange for the definition of the EOSC Interoperability Framework on data publishing and open data, User Experience – Resource Sharing and Discovery, and User Experience – Resource Composability. The activities align with the mission of EOSC Future and with the foreseen collaboration activities with INFRAEOSC-07 projects and Science Projects.”

It was under development at the time of outlining the CRAFT-OA project. In June 2023, the working group published the two main documents that became guidelines for designing solutions for the Open Journal Systems (OJS)⁴:

1. **EOSC-IF / Interoperability Guideline: Research Product Deposition.**⁵
2. **EOSC-IF Interoperability Guideline: Access to content via Persistent Identifier (PID).**⁶

2.1 Interoperability Guidelines Scenarios from the OJS Perspective

The **EOSC-IF / Interoperability Guideline: Research Product Deposition** document defines several scenarios for compatibility implementation relevant to different systems (see Figure 1 below). It focuses on the implementation of **(semi-)automatic deposition workflows of research assets** and describes **several generic scenarios** that would benefit from the **EOSC-IF for Research Product Publishing**.

² [Research Product Publishing Framework Working Group](#)

³ [EOSC Future working groups](#)

⁴ [Open Journal Systems \(OJS\) - Software - Public Knowledge Project](#)

⁵ [EOSC-IF / Interoperability Guideline: Research Product Deposition](#)

⁶ [EOSC IF Interoperability Guideline: Access to content via PID](#)

Figure 1: Scenarios that would benefit from the EOSC-IF guidelines for research product deposition as described in EOSC-IF / Interoperability Guideline: Research Product Deposition.⁷

For OJS, **Scenario 4** was evaluated as the most relevant. This conclusion reflects the typical operational practice of journal publishing systems based on OJS, where communication with external systems is usually handled directly or through metadata harvesting using standardized protocols exposed on the OJS platform. Examples include the **Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) plugin** enabling communication with the DOAJ database via the **DOAJ Application Programming Interface (API)**, the **CrossRef plugin**, or various harvesting mechanisms such as the **Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH)**, **Journal Metadata Exchange Format (JMEF) standard**⁸, or the **Signposting standard**.

Considering these established integration practices, **Scenario 4** was identified as the **most appropriate and practical approach** for publishers using OJS to manage their journals.

2.2 Interoperability Guidelines Standards from the OJS Perspective

In points **2.–5.** of the guidelines, the EOSC Working Group provides recommendations for standards that can be applied (see Table 1) to facilitate communication among systems within the EOSC ecosystem. All of these recommendations are, in principle, relevant to OJS considering the selection of **Scenario 4** as the most suitable approach. However, not all of them can be fully implemented within the current OJS environment due to technical or architectural limitations.

⁷ [EOSC-IF / Interoperability Guideline: Research Product Deposition](#)

⁸ A XML format designed to exchange information about journals between different systems, see [Journal Metadata Exchange Format](#).

Table 1: Related standards and protocols as described in EOSC-IF / Interoperability Guideline: Research Product Deposition.⁹

Related Standard	Description	Link
<i>SWORD v3</i>	To implement (semi-)automatic deposition workflows in push mode	https://sword.cottagelabs.com/swordv3/
<i>COAR Notify</i>	To implement (semi-)automatic deposition workflows in pull mode	https://www.coar-repositories.org/notify/
<i>Signposting</i>	To implement (semi-)automatic deposition workflows in pull mode	https://signposting.org/
<i>OpenAIRE Guidelines v4.0</i>	For the metadata exchange format	https://guidelines.openaire.eu/

The **EOSC-IF Interoperability Guideline: Access to content via PID**¹⁰ is focusing on accessing contents via PID and OJS is listed among supported systems.

We analysed the recommended standards and assessed their relevance and feasibility within the OJS environment, as described in the following subsections.

2.2.1 OpenAIRE Guidelines v4.0

The metadata exchange format defined in OpenAIRE Guidelines v4.0¹¹ is highly relevant from the OJS perspective and was already implemented as part of **CRAFT-OA Deliverable D6.1**¹². The **OpenAIRE Standard Plugin**¹³ extends the existing **OAI-PMH protocol** by introducing the **oai_openaire** metadata format, which enables external databases such as the **OpenAIRE Graph** to harvest article metadata directly from OJS.

This implementation ensures that metadata exposed by OJS comply with the **OpenAIRE Guidelines v4.0** requirements, thereby improving interoperability, visibility, and discoverability of research outputs published through OJS-based journals within the EOSC ecosystem.

⁹ [EOSC-IF / Interoperability Guideline: Research Product Deposition](#)

¹⁰ [EOSC IF Interoperability Guideline: Access to content via PID](#)

¹¹ [Introduction — OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers 4.0.0 documentation](#)

¹² [CRAFT-OA Deliverable 6.1 OJS Connector for OpenAIRE Research Graph](#)

¹³ [GitHub - munipress/openAIREstandard: Standard OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers v4 OJS3 plugin](#)

2.2.2 Signposting

The **Signposting protocol** is a method that uses Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) links and link headers to describe relationships between scholarly resources, such as an article, its metadata, data files, and author information. It helps machines easily discover and connect these related resources on the web. In short, it makes research outputs more **FAIR** — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

Technically, the Signposting protocol provides machine-actionable link relations (e.g., *describedby*, *item*, *cite-as*) on the specific page of a scholarly object, so that harvesting agents can unambiguously determine where metadata, content, or PID resources reside. The plugin therefore enables OJS journals to expose these link relations, improving interoperability, discoverability and extraction of structured object-constituent links for the EOSC ecosystem.

This standard is considered relevant for OJS, and the existing implementation¹⁴ of the **Signposting protocol** in earlier OJS versions served as a foundation for further development. Building on the already available functionality, the protocol was identified as a **suitable candidate for future enhancement** within the EOSC interoperability context.

The Signposting approach enables the use of machine-readable HTTP link headers to connect persistent identifiers (such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)) with related resources — including metadata, full-text content, and supplementary files. Strengthening its implementation in OJS contributes to improved **machine-actionable interoperability**, **resource discoverability**, and **metadata linking** across systems participating in the EOSC ecosystem.

2.2.3 COAR Notify

COAR Notify is a protocol that enables **interoperable notifications** between repositories and other scholarly systems (like publishers or peer-review services). It uses **Linked Data Notifications (LDN)**¹⁵ to let systems automatically inform each other about actions such as publication, review, or update. In short, it supports a **decentralized and connected research ecosystem** where repositories can communicate seamlessly.

At the time of evaluation, **COAR Notify** was not supported in **OJS**, and no implementation work had been initiated. During our consultations with the **COAR development team**, we were informed that:

“We have been having ongoing discussions with the PKP team about the implementation of COAR Notify, but have not yet come to an agreement about an implementation plan. As such, the development of COAR Notify has not yet started.”

¹⁴ [OJS plugin implementation for the Signposting patterns](#)

¹⁵ [Linked Data Notifications](#)

Further discussions with the **Public Knowledge Project (PKP) OJS development team** confirmed that the implementation of COAR Notify is **not a current priority** for PKP. The main reason is that COAR Notify is primarily designed to support workflows typical for **Overlay Journals**, which are not the main focus and user base of the OJS platform.

This conclusion was reinforced during the **Tech Event in Turin**,¹⁶ where we met representatives of the PKP programming team. They clearly stated that OJS does not intend to evolve into a platform for Overlay Journals. This position aligns with the earlier information received from the COAR development team, who confirmed that previous discussions with PKP had also not resulted in a shared implementation plan.

COAR Notify is proposed in the EOSC-IF Interoperability Guideline for the pull mode where OJS provides other alternatives (such as OAI-PMH) and Singposting is available too (see Section [1.2.2 Signposting](#) above). Considering these findings, and in agreement with the **WP6 leadership of CRAFT-OA project** and the **OpenAIRE Graph team**, we concluded that the **COAR Notify protocol will not be pursued** within the framework of this deliverable. Consequently, it will not be included as part of the OJS interoperability implementation towards the EOSC-IF Interoperability Guidelines and we will focus on SWORD v3 for support of push mode.

2.2.4 SWORD v3

SWORD version 3¹⁷ is a protocol that allows automated and standardized **deposit of digital content** into repositories. It enables systems — like journals, data platforms, or research management tools — to transfer items (such as articles or datasets) along with metadata directly into a repository. In short, it simplifies and streamlines **content ingestion and interoperability** across scholarly systems.

Version 3 represents the next evolutionary step of the **SWORD protocol**, extending and modernising the functionality previously available in version 2. Currently, only a very limited number of repository and publishing systems support version 3 of the protocol. Within OJS, there previously existed a **legacy SWORD server plugin**¹⁸ and a **SWORD v2 client plugin**,¹⁹ both offering basic interoperability for deposition workflows.

As the **EOSC-IF / Interoperability Guideline: Research Product Deposition** recommends **SWORD v3** as the preferred standard for **push deposition mode**, a **pilot implementation of the OJS SWORD v3 plugin** was developed as part of this work.

Following the conclusions drawn from the **COAR Notify** evaluation, greater emphasis was placed on the **push-mode** interoperability approach. Consequently, the development of the first prototype of the **OJS SWORD v3 plugin** was initiated to establish a foundation for future evolution in this direction.

¹⁶ [PKP Sprint and CRAFT-OA Tech Event: Advancing Open Access Publishing in Turin](#)

¹⁷ [SWORD v3](#)

¹⁸ [GitHub - quideneuf/swordServer: OJS Plugin Providing SWORD Endpoints](#)

¹⁹ [GitHub - pkp/sword: Allow Journal Managers and \(optionally\) Authors to deposit articles via the SWORD protocol](#)

Since no previous implementation of SWORD v3 for OJS existed – and given that, at this stage, there are still very few external systems capable of harvesting or receiving data through this protocol – the work carried out represents an important **starting point for future interoperability**. It is expected that as SWORD v3 gradually becomes adopted by repositories and metadata aggregators, both the functionality and usability of this OJS plugin will expand accordingly, supporting more advanced and automated deposition workflows within the EOSC ecosystem.

3 INTEROPERABILITY GUIDELINES IMPLEMENTATION FOR OJS

The following section describes the implementation and further development of three standards and protocols that were identified, during the analysis of the **EOSC Interoperability Guidelines**, as suitable for continued integration and use within **OJS**.

Since some of the recommended standards had already been implemented or developed in previous stages of the CRAFT-OA project (e.g., within Deliverable D6.1²⁰), this chapter primarily focuses on the **WORD v3 protocol**, which was newly developed and implemented as part of this deliverable. This section provides an overview of its design, functionality, and potential for future enhancement in alignment with the **EOSC-IF**.

3.1 Metadata Exchange Format

The **OpenAIRE Guidelines v4.0**²¹ define an application profile for literature, institutional and thematic repositories that supports FAIR principles — including requirements for persistent identifiers, richly described metadata, **controlled vocabularies** (e.g., access rights, resource types) and machine-readable exposure of metadata via the OAI-PMH interface.

To enable OJS journals to comply with these guidelines, a specific OJS plugin was developed. **openAIREstandard plugin**²² – described in the context of CRAFT-OA Deliverable D6.1 (*OJS Connector for OpenAIRE Research Graph*) – extends the OJS platform by introducing a new metadata format (with prefix “**oai_openaire**”) to the OAI-PMH interface and supports controlled vocabularies for resource types and access rights.²³

Key implementation features include:

- Addition of the new metadata format **oai_openaire** in the OJS OAI-PMH endpoint, enabling harvesting of metadata compliant with OpenAIRE v4.0.
- Support for **COAR vocabularies**²⁴: journals can configure each section to specify a publication type from the *COAR Resource Type vocabulary*; access rights are handled via the *COAR Access Rights Vocabulary*.

By implementing this plugin, OJS-based journals gain the following benefits in the context of the **EOSC**²⁵ ecosystem: Improved visibility of research outputs, enhanced metadata

²⁰ [CRAFT-OA Deliverable 6.1 OJS Connector for OpenAIRE Research Graph](#)

²¹ [Introduction — OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers 4.0.0 documentation](#)

²² [GitHub - munipress/openAIREstandard: Standard OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers v4 OJS3 plugin](#)

²³ [Using the OJS Connector for the OpenAIRE Graph](#)

²⁴ [COAR Vocabularies Documentation](#)

²⁵ [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\) - Research and innovation](#)

interoperability, and easier compliance with Open Science mandates. The plugin therefore forms a foundational building block in our implementation of the interoperability guidelines.

3.2 Signposting

A plugin to support Signposting protocol in OJS was developed for earlier versions of OJS, implementing the **Signposting protocol**²⁶ and published on Github by **4Science**²⁷ (plugin: **4Science/signposting**²⁸). However, the first iteration of the plugin contained various bugs and compatibility issues with newer OJS releases.

In the course of this deliverable, these issues were corrected and the plugin was adapted to newer OJS versions (3.2.1 onward). The current version supports OJS 3.2.1, 3.3.x and 3.4.x and is available (as a fork) under the Munipress GitHub repository: **munipress/signposting**.²⁹

A test installation was conducted on the Munipress-managed OJS instance **MUNI Journals**,³⁰ for example in the journal **Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace**.³¹

As the plugin is now stable for the supported OJS versions, the next steps include monitoring uptake in journals, verifying interactions with harvesting services, and refining the configuration settings so that journals can easily enable and manage Signposting-link generation.

3.3 SWORD v3

Pilot implementation of the OJS SWORD v3 plugin was developed³² based on the SWORD version 3 specification³³. The **pilot implementation** was designed with these properties:

- **Technical Requirements**
 - Support for OJS 3.5.
 - Use OJS's asynchronous jobs queue to deposit article details.
 - Support Basic (username/password) and API Key authentication modes with a SWORDv3 server.
 - Log deposit requests and responses for debugging.

²⁶ [Link Relations](#)

²⁷ [New OJS plugin for Signposting - #4 by sourcedump - Community Showcase - PKP Community Forum](#)

²⁸ [OJS plugin implementation for the Signposting patterns.](#)

²⁹ [GitHub/Munipress: Signposting plugin](#)

³⁰ [Masaryk University Journals](#)

³¹ [Cyberpsychology Singnposting Linkset 33834](#)

³² [OJS SWORD v3 plugin](#)

³³ [SWORD v3](#)

- **Deposits**
 - Deposit basic article metadata in Dublin Core (DC) format, as required by SWORDv3 spec.
 - Deposit PDF galleys.
 - Deposit and update article data every time a published article changes. Two versions will create two deposits.
 - Automatically deposit all articles as soon as they are published.
 - Allow journals to deposit all previously published articles.
- **UI and Configuration**
 - Allow journals to configure a single SWORDv3 service for deposits.
 - Test a journal's authentication credentials when a service is added.
 - A Journal Manager can see a total count of how many articles have been successfully deposited and how many articles are in pending and error states.
- Store SWORDv3's Status Document with Publication object data in OJS for debugging.

After installation described in the README.md file in the repository, you can enable the plugin in the OJS system, see Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Activation of SWORDv3 plugin in the OJS journal settings.

When the plugin is enabled, navigation to the plugin settings is available, see Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: SWORDv3 settings navigation.

The plugin settings page consists of **configuration** (setup, see Figure 4 below) and **deposition dashboard** (see Figure 5 below).

In the configuration page, you can fill in the communication endpoint of the SWORD v3 server together with the access credentials (username & password or API key).

Figure 4: SWORDv3 settings options.

The deposition dashboard tab shows the deposition statistics and allows to deposit articles and metadata to the configured SWORD v3 service.

Figure 5: SWORDv3 deposition statistics.

3.4 Access to Content via PID

As described directly in **EOSC-IF Interoperability Guideline: Access to content via PID**³⁴, OJS supports this via linksets. Communication via PID and linksets can be performed in OJS via the **Signposting protocol**, which is described in more detail in Section [2.2 Signposting](#) above.

³⁴ [EOSC IF Interoperability Guideline: Access to content via PID](#)

4 SUMMARY

This work presents a set of activities and developments carried out to align **OJS** with the **EOSC-IF on Research Product Publishing**, as defined by the **Research Product Publishing Framework Working Group**. The analysis focused on identifying which interoperability scenarios and standards are most relevant and feasible for implementation in OJS.

Based on this analysis, three standards and protocols were selected for further development and testing within the scope of this deliverable: **OpenAIRE Guidelines v4.0**, **Signposting**, and **SWORD v3**.

- The **OpenAIRE Guidelines v4.0** implementation, previously introduced in Deliverable D6.1, was validated and aligned with the latest OJS releases. The corresponding **OpenAIRE plugin** enables metadata exposure through the **oai_openaire** format, supporting harvesting by services such as the OpenAIRE Graph and ensuring compliance with FAIR principles.
- The **Signposting protocol**, initially developed for older OJS versions, was updated and stabilised to support OJS 3.2.x–3.4.x. The revised plugin allows journals (e.g., *Cyberpsychology*, hosted by MuniPress) to expose machine-readable link relations, thus improving metadata discoverability and interoperability across systems.
- The **SWORD v3** protocol was newly implemented as a pilot **OJS SWORD v3 plugin**, establishing the foundation for future **push-mode deposition workflows**. This prototype represents the first step towards enabling automated transfer of research products from OJS to external repositories in accordance with the EOSC Interoperability Guidelines.

Through these developments, this deliverable provides a **coherent set of interoperable components** that strengthen the integration of OJS within the **EOSC ecosystem**. The results form a practical baseline for further evolution of OJS plugins, facilitating seamless metadata exchange, machine-actionable linking, and automated research product deposition in line with the EOSC objectives.

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